

Student perspectives on group exams as a rehumanizing mechanism in college calculus

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College mathematics courses have historically embraced white, patriarchal norms that marginalize Black, Latin, and Indigenous students – and women, in particular (Leyva, 2021). We use Gutiérrez’s (2018) framework for rehumanizing mathematics to consider how group exams might help to shift norms related to participation and positioning of students in college calculus courses. We report on one attempt to use group exams as a rehumanizing mechanism in Calculus 2, sharing the experiences of Black, Latin*, Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander students in the class. Given the racialized and gendered history of mathematics, we then zoom in to examine a tension that emerged for several Latina and mixed-race women. We conclude by discussing the importance of seeking out the experiences of Black, Latin*, and Indigenous women and critically examining rehumanizing efforts moving forward.*

Introduction

College mathematics courses in the United States have a long history of serving as racialized and gendered spaces that have been dominated by white patriarchal norms (Leyva, 2021; McGee & Martin, 2011; Oppland-Cordell, 2014). Furthermore, schooling structures have served to separate the person from the mathematics, often making students feel dehumanized in mathematics classrooms (Gutiérrez, 2018). Thus, Gutiérrez (2018) argues for a process of rehumanizing mathematics, which entails putting the person back into the mathematics and honoring the ways in which people have been doing mathematics for years. This process of rehumanizing is especially important for Black, Latin*, and Indigenous students, who have been marginalized in mathematics classrooms; and women in these groups, in particular, given their experiences of racialized and gendered oppression (Borum & Walker, 2012; Charleston et al., 2014; Leyva, 2021; Ong et al., 2011).

The second author took up this call to rehumanize mathematics in her university Calculus 2 class. As a key element of this approach, she implemented a group exam structure into the class. While differences in structures can exist, all forms of group exams entail students taking exams—or portions of exams—in collaboration with several classmates, rather than individually. Such collaborative exam structures have the potential to improve

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student learning, support positive engagement practices (such as debate and discussion), and increase student attitudes towards classes (e.g., Bloom, 2009; Eaton, 2009; Gilley & Clarkston, 2014; Wieman et al., 2014). We propose that these structures might also serve to rehumanize mathematics and counter the white patriarchal norms that currently dominate college mathematics courses. At the same time, we must critically examine the implementation of group exam structures and, in particular, attend to the experiences of Black, Indigenous, and Latin* women. Doing so will allow us to identify potential barriers to rehumanization and optimize the use of group exams moving forward.

In this paper, we explore students' experiences with the group exam structure, with particular attention to the views of Indigenous, Black, and Latin* students. We then zoom in to examine the experiences of four mixed-race and Latina women. In particular, we investigate the following questions:

1. In what ways did Black, Latin*, and Indigenous students view group exams as rehumanizing (or not) their mathematics experience in Calculus 2?
2. What barriers did mixed-race and Latina women experience that stood in the way of group exams serving a rehumanizing function in Calculus 2?

Conceptual grounding

There is widespread concern nationally about creating inclusive mathematics classrooms and addressing issues of access, equity, and diversity in the field (Abell et al., 2017; Bressoud et al., 2015; Hagman, 2021; National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2014). At the same time, there are limitations to discussions of equity, as the term is often used to convey a value without real action taken to effect change (e.g., Castagno, 2014). Additionally, Gutiérrez highlights how equity is often viewed as a destination, instead shifting focus to the action of rehumanizing mathematics, which “reflects an ongoing process and requires constant vigilance to maintain and to evolve with contexts” (Gutiérrez, 2018, p. 4). Mathematics classroom structures that are rehumanizing serve to disconnect students from simple compliance and reconnect them with the joy of doing mathematics, with a focus on Latin*, Indigenous, and Black students. Rehumanizing practices seek to transform the balance of power in the classroom and intentionally create a space where students feel a sense of belonging. Being guided by a rehumanizing approach entails acknowledging that human beings have always been doing mathematics in their daily lives in meaningful ways.

For educators who want to heed this call, Gutiérrez suggests eight possible domains of attention that constitute a sort of framework for ways in which we can rehumanize mathematics. These include “(1) participation/positioning, (2) cultures/histories, (3) windows/mirrors, (4) living practice, (5) creation, (6) broadening mathematics, (7) body/emotions and (8) ownership” (Gutiérrez, 2018, p. 4). Of particular interest for this paper is the first category, participation and positioning. This domain focuses on challenging the historical classroom power dynamic between teachers as authority figures and students as vessels into which teachers pour information. Rehumanizing efforts seek to upend that power dynamic and

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replace it with more discussion-based classrooms where students view themselves and their peers as doers of mathematics, seeking evaluation and approval from each other as well as the teacher, rather than only from the teacher. Through the implementation of group exams, the second author sought to make exactly these kinds of shifts in her classroom to change how students viewed each other and their relation to mathematics.

Attempts to rehumanize mathematics must also take into consideration the long history of mathematics as a racialized and gendered space (e.g., Leyva, 2017; Leyva et al., 2021; Martin, 2006). Mathematics classrooms have been guided by white patriarchal norms that emphasize individualism and competition (e.g., Leyva, 2021). Given the way in which whiteness has served as an organizing construct not only in mathematics but in education overall and society at large (Leonardo, 2002, 2004), we focus on the influence of whiteness as a racial category, rather than delving into ethnic identities within whiteness. We align with Leonardo (2002) who highlights how “whiteness as a privileged signifier has become global” (p. 30), the world has been created according to white ideals, and white folks must acknowledge their racial privilege. Thus, in our own positionality statement below, we identify our whiteness, rather than our ethnicities, given the primary influence of our whiteness on our experiences in mathematics throughout our lives.

Finally, when we apply this lens of rehumanizing mathematics in a racialized, gendered context to exam structures, we must grapple with the role of exams in the political economy of schooling (Pais, 2013). As Pais notes, “schools are places of social selection and teachers are agents of exclusion” (p. 30), with exams being a key mechanism for carrying out that exclusion. As we seek to rehumanize exams, we are cognizant of their role in a system that stratifies and dehumanizes. At the same time, instructors face many constraints, and there are often limits to what can be changed in college courses. Thus, here we choose to explore ways to improve the exam structure, while continuing to think critically about the function of exams in the current system and potential structural changes as we move forward in this work.

Author positionality

Aligning with folks who urge mathematics education researchers to be explicit about how our identities influence our research (Aguirre et al., 2017), here we briefly describe our positionality in relation to this work. Both authors identify as white, cisgender women—one situated in an education department and the other in a mathematics department. Both of us have experienced mathematics as patriarchal and exclusionary in various spaces as a result of our gender; at the same time, we have never felt alienated or oppressed in mathematics as the result of our race. We come to this work seeking pathways for rehumanizing mathematics, recognizing both the limitations of our own experiences and the need to listen to students whose voices are not often centered in conversations about mathematics classroom practices.

Course context

Data for these analyses come from two sections of Calculus 2 taught by the second author at a predominantly white institution in Fall 2018. The course is taken by engineering, science, and math majors and taught from a calculus text focusing on computation and applications that has been used by the university for roughly 30 years. As part of an effort to implement more humane pedagogies and work to rehumanize calculus, the instructor incorporated several changes into the course over a five-year period including a class mission statement, active-learning strategies, small group discussions to work on math problems in every class period, and group exams. Additionally, the instructor provided guidelines and resources about productive and respectful group discussion strategies (e.g., giving others time to think, allowing group members to arrive at different conclusions). The exam structure entailed both group and solo portions of each exam, with the group portion typically occurring the class period prior to the solo portion. During the group portion, students could troubleshoot, collaborate, and debate with group members; however, each student turned in their own exam, allowing them to come to their own conclusions. Groups changed for each exam and were semi-randomly created (see Dobie & MacArthur, in press for additional details about group creation).

Data collection

Three surveys were administered throughout the semester to elicit students' perspectives on the course structure, group exams, and ideas about rehumanizing mathematics. Across both sections, 216 students (90%) submitted responses to at least one survey. Of those 216 students, the breakdown of reported identities included 71.3% white, 14% Asian, 9% Hispanic or Latin*, 2.7% mixed race, 1% Black, 1% Middle Eastern, and 0.5% Pacific Islander or Native Hawaiian students. Of those students who reported their race and/or ethnicity, 29% identified as female, 70% identified as male, and 1% didn't report their gender identity.

Following analysis of survey results, six women were invited to participate in follow-up interviews. These women were selected based on two criteria: 1) identification as Latin* or mixed race (there were no exclusively Black or Indigenous women in the class) and 2) current enrollment in university courses (so that we could easily contact the students). We chose to interview these women due to Gutiérrez's call to gather "evidence from those for whom we seek to rehumanize our practices that, in fact, the practices are felt in that way" (Gutiérrez, 2018, pp. 3-4). Since several of these women were among the few to express any negative sentiments towards group exams—and also the exact population of students for whom the instructor sought to rehumanize calculus—we felt it was important to learn more about their experiences. Four of the six women accepted the interview invitation: Denise and Sofia identified as Hispanic/Latina; Lilly identified as white, Hispanic, and Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander; and Selena identified as white, Asian, and Pacific Islander (all names are pseudonyms). Individual interviews were conducted via Zoom by one of the two authors in Fall 2020 and lasted between 46 and 86 minutes. Questions focused on four

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primary areas: overall experiences in their major and with university mathematics courses, experiences in Calculus 2, survey responses from Calculus 2 focused on group exams and rehumanizing mathematics, and the role of identity in STEM learning experiences.

Data analysis

Given our interest in the potential of group exams to rehumanize students' mathematics experiences, one survey question was selected for analysis for this study: "In your experience, describe how the group portion of the exams has made the classroom/learning environment more or less humane for students, compared to more traditionally structured exams." Each author coded all 196 responses to this question as either positive (if the student supported group exams and/or expressed a belief that they made the learning environment more humane), negative (if the student opposed the group exam structure and/or expressed a belief that it made the learning environment less humane), and neutral/mixed (if the student's response was neither positive nor negative, or if the student shared both positive and negative responses). All points of disagreement were discussed, and we agreed on one final code for each student. We then calculated frequencies and percentages of responses in each category for a) the class as a whole and b) all students who identified as Black, Latin*, Pacific Islander, or Native Hawaiian; or mixed race including one of those identities (23/196 students).

After the four interviews with mixed race and Latina women were conducted, each interview was transcribed, and both authors read through all transcripts, engaging in an open-coding process (Strauss, 1987). Emergent themes were discussed, and four coding categories were selected for the purposes of this analysis: interaction with and relation to peers in the course, reported challenges with group exams, expectations for group members, and expectations for oneself when working with others. A detailed coding scheme was developed and again both authors coded each interview, comparing points of disagreement until each was resolved.

Findings

Here we first explore students' reflections on whether group exams made the Calculus 2 learning environment more or less humane, drawing on survey responses. Then we dive into one theme that emerged from interviewees, unfulfilled group expectations.

Student reflections on the humane-ness of group exams

Overwhelmingly, students viewed group exams as positive and as contributing to a more humane learning environment than traditional solo exams. Out of the 196 students who responded to the aforementioned survey question, 81% provided responses indicating that the group portion of exams made the learning environment more humane, while only 1.5% of students suggested that the shift made the learning environment less humane. The remaining 17.5% of responses were either mixed, with students reporting both positive and negative impacts of group exams, or neutral.

For the 23 Black, Latin*, Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander students who responded to the survey question, 17 students (74%) provided positive responses, suggesting that the group portion of the exams made the learning environment more humane; five students (22%) provided neutral or mixed responses; and one student (4%) answered negatively. Below we explore the nature of some of these positive responses, and then we investigate some reasons for the neutral, mixed, and negative comments among this population of students.

Many of the positive survey responses from students in this subgroup centered on the community-oriented benefits of being able to work with and learn from each other. One Black male student wrote, "I think it makes the classroom more humane since you're adding a group collaboration aspect to the exam," while a male student who identified as a Native Hawaiian reported that the group exams felt "more 'humane' because the collaboration was fun and I was able to learn how others use the same math." Survey responses also highlighted perspective-expanding experiences with the group exams, as can be seen in one response from a Latino male student who wrote that he "get[s] to see how others might approach problems and try to understand them differently."

Students also articulated the two-way benefits of group exams since they are able to both help and be helped by others. One Latina woman commented that if students cannot "comprehend a certain detail of the problem," then they have other people in their group to "explain and help you out." Additionally, this same student noted that "you are also able to help others," showcasing the give-and-take of group exams. Another female student who identifies as white, Hispanic, and Native Hawaiian also mentioned that "if you're stuck someone else in your group might be able to explain it and visa [sic] versa," adding, "it's really a good teamwork experience."

While students' reported experiences were positive overall, it is critical that we closely examine the neutral, mixed, and negative responses, as we recognize the potential for further oppression and harm to Indigenous, Black, and Latin* students given the strong role of interaction with others during group exams. When examining the neutral, mixed, and negative comments from the subgroup of students more closely, we discovered that such comments came primarily from women (5 of 6 responses). There were nine Latina and mixed-race women who responded to the survey overall, meaning that five of nine (55.6%) provided neutral, mixed, or negative responses about the group exams, with only 44.4% providing positive responses—a drastically lower percentage than found among all other groups of students.

Upon examining these comments more closely, the primary theme that emerged was concern regarding the lack of preparation of one's groupmates. Four of the five women mentioned something akin to "some students are not prepared," with one Latina woman also expressing concern that she might be "not prepared enough" or might not "understand things as much as i [sic] should." Another Latina woman who provided a mixed response broadened this perspective on a lack of preparation to include group member attitudes, writing that "when group members actually try," her experience has been "very positive"; however, "when they are not prepared nor have a positive attitude, i [sic] feel it negatively impacts

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me.” This mention of the lack of a positive attitude suggests broader concern about group member relations and interactions.

A challenge to group exams as a rehumanizing mechanism: unfulfilled expectations of group members

Individual interviews with four of the aforementioned women allowed us to further investigate these reported issues with group members, particularly around perceived preparation. A more nuanced theme emerged from the coded interviews related to the women’s expectations for themselves and others in group exams. In particular, three of the four women commented on experiences where they had to carry the weight of their team, and the burden they experienced in doing so. Denise captured this experience in the following excerpt:

When a student isn’t prepared or, like, when one of your group members isn’t prepared, and then it impedes your conversation with other group members who attempt to be prepared but may also not be prepared at all, what you end up getting is nothing and what you end up giving is everything.

This sense of “getting...nothing” and “giving...everything” was echoed by Sofia when she shared about two teammates who would “stare at the questions but they weren’t willing to help.” She explained how she was “annoyed” because “I felt like I was writing the whole time trying to figure out the problems without getting a lot of help.” Similarly, when Selena reflected on her group exam experiences, she recalled, “I was usually the one helping people instead of being the one helped.”

As part of this discussion about group member roles, the three women also conveyed a sense of responsibility to their teams. Sofia captured this notion when describing how she spent more time studying for group exams than solo exams, noting, “If I had to, I would carry the group.” For Denise and Selena, this sense of responsibility came through as they discussed their desire for teammates to challenge their ideas and their concern about failing the team when others don’t challenge them. Selena shared,

Every time there was some kind of discrepancy between our work they would just be like, “Oh, well you’re probably right” instead of actually thinking about how they were wrong or how they could be right or I could be wrong... I’m not going to go in thinking that I did everything right, especially when it was my first time learning these things, and the fact that they kind of were so, like, deflated to the point where they didn’t even want to question me made me think, well, I’m going to take down the rest of my team like this because I don’t know if I’m right and no one is questioning anything.

Here Selena conveyed a concern of “tak[ing] down the rest of my team” due to the fact that she was the only one doing the work, and no one was challenging her. Denise also expressed frustration that her team members “wouldn’t call you out,” which was something she “really wished for.” She added, “I feel bad cause in the sense of, I don’t even know if that answer is right, which is why I was trying to ask questions to them.”

Interestingly, despite the challenges experienced and the frustration caused by group members' lack of participation and commitment to the team, three of the four women reported positive feelings towards group exams now, and one (Denise) described her group experience on the exams as "relatively good" overall.

Discussion

Native Hawaiian, Pacific Islander, Latin*, and Black students' reported experiences on group exams in calculus reveal many perceived affordances that align with ideas in the Participation/Positioning category of the rehumanizing framework (Gutiérrez, 2018). In particular, students reported appreciating the opportunity to collaborate with peers, see others' perspectives, and both help and be helped by others. At the same time, some Latina and mixed-race women in the course reported frustration at having to carry the weight of their team due to team members not fulfilling their expectations. This frustration was accompanied by a sense of responsibility to the team, as well as a desire to be challenged by their team members. In contrast with some students whose frustrations were embedded in deficit-based language and judgements about their peers' abilities (Dobie & MacArthur, in press), it is notable that none of these women made assumptions about what their teammates were capable of. Sometimes these women even gave their classmates the benefit of the doubt, as when Denise spoke about students who "attempt to be prepared but may... not be prepared."

These findings highlight the ways in which group exams serve to restructure possibilities for participation and positioning, providing a potential rehumanizing mechanism in college mathematics courses. However, with opportunities for more student collaboration comes the possibility of racialized and gendered mechanisms (e.g., Leyva et al., 2021) playing out within student groups. While none of the women who were interviewed attributed their increased responsibility and lack of engagement from group members to their race or gender, these findings raise questions about potential extra burdens placed on mixed race and Latina women in group exam formats. We believe these questions should not cause us to abandon group exam formats, especially since most of the Latina and mixed-race women still supported group exams and identified many benefits of such structures. Rather, it is imperative that as we move forward in this work we continue to seek out the voices of Latina, Indigenous, and Black women; and especially to take an intersectional lens and explore the experiences of Black women, who are often erased in analyses (Crenshaw, 1989) and who were not represented in this study. Additionally, we must systematically examine who is served by group exam structures and work to identify and address any oppressive and hierarchical structures that emerge within groups. By doing this work, we can take next steps in considering mechanisms for improving group exam structures to further rehumanize mathematics for Black, Latin*, and Indigenous students, and women, in particular.

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